

Information Theory and Statistical Mechanics (Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis etc)

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Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distributions and even expressions of Shannon's entropy emerged in the 1800s and early 1900s with Maxwell, Boltzmann and Gibbs and others. Later, in the 1980s, Tsallis suggested a non-MB distribution and many other such distributions have been developed since. It has been argued in (1) that conservation of energy in two body collisions and kinematics are all that are necessary for obtaining these new distributions i.e. the concept of maximization of entropy is not needed. Nevertheless, the "maximization" of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on overall energy does yield the MB distribution. This begs the question: Why does an information theoretical approach lead to the same result as a physical two body elastic collision scheme? Secondly, why does information theory lead to the MB result and not to other distributions? (One should note that for other distributions, entropy functions have been created such that their maximization subject to constant energy and particle number yield the new distributions, but such entropy expressions seem to be mathematical constructs.)

MB Distribution from a Collision Point of View

Consider a gas in equilibrium with a total energy E and many two body-collisions such that: $e_1 + e_2 \rightarrow e_3 + e_4$ where $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ i.e. the collisions are elastic. (1) has discussed the problem of assuming non-elastic collisions. Next, consider that the probability for e_1 to collide with e_2 is the product $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ i.e. an "and" probability situation. This seems to be a key idea namely that kinematics directly matches probability theory. This need not be the case as Kaniadakis (2) points out. For example, e_1 changing to e_3 might be proportional to $f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]$ (i.e. due to fermion exclusion). Then, there is no longer a simple link to probability theory i.e. maximization of Shannon's entropy. To maintain equilibrium, one may argue a time reversal balance i.e. :

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking the \ln of ((1)) yields a conservation law which one may identify with conservation of energy. (What other function of energy is conserved without energy being conserved?) Then: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. There is no need for entropy or its maximization to obtain this result.

Shannon's Information Theory Approach

Shannon's information theory introduces an entropy expression - $\sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$ where f_i is a probability. The theory is said to be related to "transmission of information" (3) where information is defined by $\ln(1/f_i)$. In other words, one may consider, as in (3), "a long sequence of independent and identically distributed outcomes" $a=(x_1, x_2 \dots x_N)$

If N is large, then x_i appears $N f_i$ times and the probability for an outcome sequence is:

$$\text{Prob}(a) = \text{Product over } i \text{ } f_i^{Nf_i}$$

$$\text{so } \ln(\text{Prob}(a)) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(Nf_i) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(f_i) + \ln(N)$$

$$\text{Or : } \text{Prob}(a) = N \exp(\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(f_i)) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is very much like conservation equation from two particle scattering ((1)).

Thus, for different sets of f_i (i.e. the probability), different values of $\text{Prob}(a)$ are obtained. A certain set of f_i will maximize $\text{Prob}(a)$ and this set is related to the extremum of the entropy: $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(f_i)$

It seems the choice of f_i limits or constricts changes which could occur in a system. For example, if $f_i = \text{constant}$, then all states are physically constrained to having the same likelihood. If one were to relax this constraint, one would see non-identical f_i 's emerging. If the conserved quantity ((2)) measures in a sense the freedom for changes or activity in a system, then one could maximize it (subject to any known constraints) to find the most "free" distribution. This seems to be the philosophy behind Shannon's maximization of entropy of approach. If one has a set of f_i which maximize $P(a)$, this set may not be realized in a physical system because of physical constraints. In other restrictions in the kinematics of two body collisions may prevent the achievement of a state which maximizes probability i.e. Shannon's entropy.

How could one apply Shannon's entropy maximization to a physical gas? One might consider a single gas particle changing energies with each collision (or not colliding in a time dt). This might lead to the vector $a = (e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots)$ and ((2)). One has to be careful, however, about the idea of maximization. In the case of ((1)), it is assumed that $f_1 f_2 = f_3 f_4$ ((3)). As noted, this mimics "and" probability theory exactly and so a connection with ((2)) can, it seems, be made. If the physical two body collisions do not follow ((3)) (due to the fermion exclusion principle etc), then the idea of fermion exclusion would need to be included as a constraint in Shannon's entropy maximization, and this may or may not be easily done. Simply maximizing Shannon's entropy seems to imply that only probability (i.e. ((3))) governs physical changes that may occur within a system.

Thus maximizing:

- $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(f_i) + b_1 \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f_i$ ((4)) where b_1 is Lagrange multiplier and e_i energy yields the same result as the two body collision approach, but only because the physical two body collisions mimic "and" probability and allow for the achievement of the highest probability state.

Geometric Considerations

Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$ also has a geometric interpretation it seems. It may be seen as the dot product of the vector $\{f_i\}$ with the vector $\{\ln(f_i)\}$. Note: $\sum_i f_i = 1$ (normalization) and so if one changes $f_i \rightarrow f_i + df_i$ then $\sum_i df_i = 0$ if $f_i + df_i$ is to be normalized.

Consider the dot product of $\{f_i\}$ with a constant vector $\{c_i\}$ i.e. $\sum_i f_i c_i$. If one changes f_i to $f_i + df_i$, this dot product changes by:

$$\sum_i c_i df_i \quad ((5))$$

Next, consider the dot product with a vector $\{G(f_i)\}$ then changing f_i to $f_i + df_i$ changes the dot product by:

$$\{df_i\} \cdot \{G(f_i)\} + \{f_i\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{d}{df_i} G(f_i) df_i \right\} \quad ((6))$$

If one wishes the same appearance as ((5)) then the second term of ((6)) should be 0. A solution is $G(f_i) = \ln(f_i)$ because the second term becomes $\sum_i df_i = 0$. Thus, the vector $\{\ln(f_i)\}$ ensures that small changes df_i yield a new vector orthogonal to first order to $\{f_i\}$.

This is interesting because Shannon's entropy changes just like $\{f_i\} \cdot \{c_i\}$. Now c_i may be a function of energy for example. Thus, maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint $\{f_i\} \cdot \{c_i\}$ yields a solution:

$$\{\ln(f_i)\} = \{c_i\} \text{ with a possible solution of } \ln(f_i) = c_i \text{ or for the physics case } \ln(f(e)) = -e/T.$$

The fact that the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint $\{f_i\} \cdot \{c_i\}$ is $\ln(f_i) = c_i$ suggests this result may appear as a solution of a physical process i.e. kinematics such as ((1)).

Non MB Distributions

It is seen in the literature that there are non MB distributions such as the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions to name two of many. These do not follow from the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on energy. We have tried to argue above that this may be due to extra constraints in the system. For example, ((1)) is a simple relationship which mimics "and" probability and so matches Shannon's entropy exactly. Fermion exclusion, however, may lead to kinematics for $e_1 + e_2 \rightarrow e_3 + e_4$ (elastic) such as:

$$f_1(1-f_3) f_2(1-f_4) = f_3(1-f_1) f_4(1-f_2) \quad ((7))$$

This may lead to a conservation equation of the form:

$$\ln(k(f_1)) + \ln(k(f_2)) = \ln(k(f_3)) + \ln(k(f_4)) \quad (8) \text{ where } k \text{ is a function}$$

For conservation of energy, $\ln(k(f_i)) = e_i$ and it is k which comes from the physical kinematics which largely defines the distribution. One may, however, construct a mathematical function such that the variation of d/df of this function subject to the constraint of constant energy yields the non-MB distribution. In the literature (2), however, this seems to be done by introducing an integral df which cancels the operation d/df and so $d/df \int df F_n(f) + b_1 d/df \int e = 0$ or $F_n(f) = e$ i.e. F_n and f are inverse functions. It might perhaps be interesting to see the entropy “created” strictly from probability and constraint arguments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, physical systems in equilibrium seem to be based on physical processes such as two body scattering which is elastic and contains a certain set of kinematical restrictions. Shannon’s entropy seems to be related to maximizing the probability of a state based on “and” probability. Only in the case for which physical kinematical constraints are identical to this “and” probability, for example the MB case where $f_1 f_2 = f_3 f_4$, does one have Shannon’s approach of maximizing entropy given by $-\sum_i f_i \ln(f_i)$ yield the distribution. In other cases, kinematics govern the distribution and Shannon’s maximum entropy state is not realized, but one may mathematically construct a function such that $d/df \int df s(f)$ subject to an energy constraint yields the distribution f .

References

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